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Gamification and E-Commerce: Examining the Impact on Customer Engagement and Online Purchase Intention

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ABSTRACT

The current investigation explores the influence of gamification elements (rewards, points, enjoyment) on customer engagement and online purchase intention considering Pakistan's dynamic e-commerce environment. The research aims to contribute towards academic understanding and practical applications by facilitating businesses upgrade their digital marketing strategies for Pakistani market. Data is collected through a structured questionnaire to ensure response reliability and validity. This study considers university students as the target audience, mainly selected because they are generally tech-savvy, and comfortable with online shopping. A multistage sampling approach is used. First, seven public universities from a specific region are selected. Then, within those universities, a snowball sampling method is utilized to reach more students especially those who might not be easily contacted through traditional means. The research uses the Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) framework to explore how customer engagement acts as a bridge between gamification elements and the online purchase intention. The findings reveal that gamification features specifically points and enjoyment significantly impact customer engagement. Subsequently, increased customer engagement proceeds to a stronger intention to purchase. The current investigation presents novel insights regarding how gamification can be effectively used in digital marketing. The results suggest that integrating gamified elements in online shopping leads to greater customer engagement and enhanced sales.

Keywords: Gamification, Points, Rewards, Enjoyment, Customer Engagement, Online Purchase Intention

JEL Classification

M30, M31, M10, M39, M37

Introduction

Due to a greater shift towards digital buying across the globe, online shopping has become a major part of daily life (Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). The extensive adoption of smartphones, accompanied by high quality internet access, has added to a visible change in consumer behavior regarding ecommerce. People are fascinated by the ease and convenience of browsing and purchasing products from their digital devices (smartphones or computers) without any time constraint or location (Laudon and Traver, 2020). One of the most noticeable shifts in the e-commerce landscape has been the fast growth of online shopping platforms offering a wide variety of product categories, ranging from electronics and fashion to groceries and household essentials, all in one place. This development has been additionally reinforced by the spread of digital payment systems and the availability of cash-on-delivery options, which have facilitated to lessen traditional barriers of online purchasing. These developments contributed to enhanced consumer confidence by providing superior flexibility and perceived security during transactions. It has become critical for businesses to completely understand the motivations which drive their customers and also to capture the factors which makes them "walk away", keeping the fact that the trend of online shopping is growing every day. By staying updated with customer's changing preferences and behaviors, companies can refine their strategies and get the most out of the digital marketplace.

In the face of the considerable expansion of online shopping, many companies still continue to face challenges in understanding their digital customers and getting meaningfully engaged with them. The major concern for companies is to acquire deep

customer engagement in an increasingly competitive marketplace and at the same time maintain longstanding loyalty. As a response to such pressure, an increasing number of organizations are focusing on gamification, an approach that integrates game-like elements into non-game contexts to improve user motivation and encourage active participation (Miri and Macke, 2022). Gamification offers organizations an opportunity to appeal their customer attention, boost engagement, and build deeper connections with their brand, by incorporating elements like rewards, points, challenges, and entertainment. As a result of growing digital platforms and online shopping trends, comprehending the impact of gamification on customer behavior in online environments becomes imperative for businesses who wish to stay competitive (Koivisto and Hamari, 2019). Organizations utilizing gamifications strategies and interactive purchasing experiences have acquired increase customer engagement and a positive impact on their purchasing decisions (Yang, Asaad and Dwivedi, 2017).

Regardless of its increasing popularity, there is still a need for more exploration to fully comprehend the impact of gamification on consumer behavior, especially considering the environment of online shopping platforms. Few studies so far have investigated the influence of gamification elements on customer engagement. For instance, Tsou and Putra, (2023) examined this relationship through Shopee Games, Indonesia's leading gamification platform in e-commerce. While this research proposes valuable insights regarding the role of gamification during the shopping experience, the findings may be inspired by cultural factors which are exclusive to the Indonesian market, thereby underscoring the need for research in other regional contexts. Such regional particularities may limit the applicability of the findings to other markets with distinct consumer behaviors and economic environments. From both theoretical and practical standpoints, there remains a significant gap in the literature, underscoring the need for continued exploration in this area. To address this gap, the present study investigates the impact of gamification features on customer engagement and purchase intention, with particular attention to the mediating role of customer engagement. The outcomes of this research could assist businesses in crafting more effective gamification strategies aimed at increasing customer engagement, boosting online sales, and achieving a stronger competitive position in the digital economy. Based on these considerations, this study seeks to answer the following research questions:

What is the impact of gamification elements, such as rewards, points, and enjoyment, on customer engagement in online shopping?

To what extent does customer engagement mediate the relationship between different gamification elements (e.g., points, rewards, enjoyment) and online purchase intention? This study makes noteworthy contributions to both theoretical knowledge and practical applications. By examining how gamification elements such as rewards, points, and enjoyment influence consumer engagement and online purchase intentions, it offers a meaningful addition to the existing body of literature. It addresses the limited empirical evidence surrounding the implementation and effectiveness of gamification strategies in digital marketing, with a focus on the e-commerce sector. Beyond its academic value, this research also provides actionable insights for businesses aiming to enhance user experience and positively shape customer behaviors in digital environments. This research makes a valuable contribution to the literature by empirically investigating how various gamification elements influence customer behavior within online retail environments. Moreover, the results offer practical insights for businesses operating in the digital marketplace. Marketing professionals may design beneficial strategies by better comprehending the role of gamification's elements in enhancing customer engagement and encouraging online purchase intention. Eventually, businesses can

utilize these insights to develop loyalty programs and engagement initiatives that may lead to improved customer relationships and increased sales.

Literature Review

Gamification and Influencing Factors

E-commerce is a revolutionary idea made possible with internet technology, altering the consumer buying behavior at its core (Kuswanto et al., 2019). The recent past has witnessed tremendous growth in online consumption worldwide, driven primarily by increased internet penetration and its increased role in daily life. As interfaces move towards digital media, making them interactive and user-friendly, consumption online is fast becoming a desirable consumer behavior worldwide (Keisidou, Sarigiannidis and Maditinos, 2011). With the fast-changing digital world of today, marketers are compelled to develop strategies that not only increase customers' engagement but also purchase intentions, thereby providing an enriched and satisfying purchasing experience (So et al., 2016). Gamification has been found to be an effective strategy employed to increase users' enjoyment and satisfy customers' psychological needs. This strategy has been observed to have a positive impact on customer engagement as well as their purchasing intention (Xu, Wu and Li, 2020). Gamification refers to the process of applying game mechanics to different platforms and applications in innovative ways to increase user experience and engagement (Tobon et al., 2020), it also plays a critical role in driving social influence, inducing recognition, and forming a sense of mutual engagement among the users (Rakhmanita, Kusumawardhani and Anggarini, 2023). Rewards, points, challenges, and pleasure are components that drive customer engagement positively (Tsou and Putra, 2023). When instant gamification is introduced, the connection becomes clear between heightened motivation and enhanced customer engagement (Alsawaier, 2018). Game mechanics and dynamics are designed to engage players to do something, thereby turning them into effective drivers of human behavior. Mechanics like achievements, appointments, bonuses, levels, and points have a tendency to drive decisions and encourage players (Gupta and Gomathi, 2017). Designing gamified experiences is now becoming a marketing strategy because gamification can impact consumers' behavior and aid companies to stand out in a competitive environment (Torres, Augusto and Neves, 2022). To keep customers engaged, marketing experts have started incorporating gamification elements into online shopping websites. Therefore, increasing numbers of companies are adopting game-based strategies and reward systems to engage their followers (Yang, Asaad and Dwivedi, 2017). Gamification has the power to impact purchase intentions by making products or services seem more valuable to customers (Gao and Wu, 2022). Besides that, it impacts users' purchase intentions by activating their motivation, and that also makes a positive contribution to purchase intentions (Mucollari and Samokhin, 2017).

Theoretical Orientation of the Study

This research employs the Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) theory within the context of consumer behavior shopping websites. As per the theory, stimulus and psychological factors combine to bring about a response (Russell and Mehrabian, 1974). A stimulus is any factor that triggers behavioral reactions (Eroglu, Machleit and Davis, 2003) and plays a key role in consumer decision-making (Su and Swanson, 2017). An organism refers to the cognitive processes and emotions of an individual (Fan, Han and Gao, 2022) while response encapsulates psychological reactions, attitudes and intentions to act (Xu et al., 2020). The S-O-R model emphasizes internal psychological aspects to the S-O-R model responses brought out by consumers (Sung et al., 2022). It

was initially developed for understanding the consumer decision-making process in traditional stores (Robert and John, 1982) albeit has been adopted in the online retail context (Park and Lennon, 2009). The S-O-R theory has been applied in other business studies to examine how constructs of gamification are stimuli (Tsou and Putra, 2023), customer engagement as organism (Naqvi et al., 2021) and purchase intention as response (Zhu et al., 2020).

Hypotheses Development & Conceptual Framework

The mechanics of gamification, in particular rewards, facilitate customer engagement and strongly contribute towards fostering brand loyalty (da Rocha Seixas et al., 2016). Companies are able to efficiently capture consumer attention through active engagement and interaction due to rewards, resulting in repeat purchases (Nicholson, 2015). Brand loyalty schemes clearly depict a direct relationship whereby customer satisfaction is improved alongside increase in repurchase intention and positive endorsements (Högberg et al., 2019). Emotion bonding is also enhanced through specially tailored brand loyalty schemes which leads to greater brand attachment and long term loyalty (Meyer-Waarden, Bruwer and Galan, 2023). It has been proven that loyalty schemes that incorporate game features capture interest more by increasing the level of fun and overall satisfaction among consumers (Hwang and Choi, 2020). Therefore, this study proposes that:

H1: Reward element of gamification positively affects the customer engagement.

As identified by Sailer et al., (2017) points represent the most basic level of gamification and increase user activity and engagement. Long-term involvement is aided by processes like earning points which are awarded based on users taking certain actions (Xi and Hamari, 2020). The frequent application of point systems has been proven to produce a positive effect on learning performance Ares et al., (2018) and overall engagement (Chang and Wei, 2016). In the area of e-commerce, point-based gamification directly affects customer engagement and is a major factor in retention (García-Jurado et al., 2021). Points are one of the most engaging aspects of gamification because they provide feedback on performance, which boosts perceptions of autonomy, fosters healthy competition, and cumulatively enhances intrinsic motivation (Chans and Portuguez Castro, 2021). Points also enhance engagement in mobile apps by adding a social dimension, learning, and fun (Jung, Lee and Leitch, 2024). Luxury brands such as Burberry have successfully implemented point-based systems with luxury rewards to increase the overall shopping experience (Falco, 2020). Likewise, the hotel industry also makes use of points and badges to improve loyalty programs and increase customer engagement (Parapanos and Michopoulou, 2023). Based on the above, the study anticipates that:

H2: Points element of gamification positively affects the customer engagement.

Gamification boosts loyalty schemes through greater enjoyment and satisfaction of reward anticipation, which, in turn, boosts both perceived hedonic and utilitarian value for customers (Bravo, Catalán and Pina, 2023). Additional, self-focused rewards appreciably boost participation by increasing enjoyment and increasing sense of personal achievement (Hwang and Choi, 2020). Organizations can boost consumer participation through the creation of positive emotions such as enjoyment, pleasure, and fun (Leclercq, Poncin and Hammedi, 2020). Enjoyment in gamified systems assists in sustaining player participation (Mullins and Sabherwal, 2020). It also influences brand perception and deepens customer engagement (Yang, Asaad and Dwivedi, 2017). Gamification approaches deepen the psychological experience of enjoyment, thereby boosting overall participation (Koivisto and Hamari, 2019). Emotionally and

cognitively involved customers are apt to participate more actively in various activities, boosting their engagement with brands (Bozkurt, Gligor and Gligor, 2022). Also, entertainment, pleasure, and enjoyment serve as fundamental drivers of consumer participation on social media platforms (Chen et al., 2021). Based on these, the following hypothesis is developed:

H3: Enjoyment element of gamification positively affects the customer engagement.

Consumer behavior, technological innovation, and information characteristics all have a positive influence on consumers' purchase intentions (Yusuf, Che Hussin and Busalim, 2018). Those consumers who are actively engaging with online communities have a greater likelihood of purchasing products or services through these communities (Prentice, Wang and Loureiro, 2019). Earlier studies investigated the impacts of social media customer engagement on purchase intentions, emphasizing drivers like attraction, social interaction, information exchange, and surveillance. The results showed that the drivers have a strong positive influence on customer engagement, and customer engagement has a positive influence on purchase intentions (Yoong and Lian, 2019). In the context of online marketing with live video, customer engagement, follower increase, and purchase intention all interrelate positively and strongly (Clement et al., 2021). Additionally, some other researchers pointed out that brand engagement positively impacts consumers' intentions to purchase the respective brand (Hwang and Choi, 2020). It is well recognized that customer engagement can effectively stimulate sustainable purchasing intentions (Gong et al., 2023). Moreover, a firm's sustainability reputation, along with customer engagement, strongly influences purchase intentions. It has also been documented that customers' online engagement impacts their intention to purchase and their willingness to pay a premium for the product (Amin et al., 2023). It is from these findings that the hypothesis is developed as follows:

H4: Customer engagement has a positive influence on the online purchase intention of the customer.

Figure 1
 Conceptual Framework
 Note: Created by the author

Literature reveals that customer engagement serves as a mediator, influencing consumer beliefs and behavioral intentions throughout brand interactions (Harrigan et al., 2017). Previous research has also revealed that customer engagement positively mediates between commitment and trust (Rather, Hollebeek and Islam, 2019). Later, research has revealed that customer engagement serves as a mediator between place attachment, place authenticity, and consumer co-creation, trust, and loyalty. Moreover, the incorporation of gamification aspects has been proven to increase consumers' willingness to buy (Lee et al., 2023). Hence, the extent to which gamification is incorporated into a brand's strategy can infer customers' attitudes toward the brand and service experience, eventually influencing their purchase intentions. According to Merrilees, (2016), hedonic users are more likely to interact and exhibit a willingness to engage in purchase behavior due to self-centered reasons whilst in comparison, functional participants depend on some rational advantages of engaging in the contest. Thus, customer engagement plays a pivotal role in purchase decisions. By incorporating gamification elements, businesses encourage active customer participation, which positively impacts the S-O-R model, leading to greater engagement and influencing online purchasing behavior. Therefore, by integrating this perspective with the arguments presented in H1 to H4, the hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H5: Customer engagement mediates the relationship of gamification elements (a) Rewards, (b) Points, (c) Enjoyment and online purchase intention.

Materials and Methods

Population and Sampling

The target population for this study consists of university students who engage in online shopping. This group is selected due to its familiarity with technology and inclination toward online purchasing (Rehman et al., 2019). To effectively manage a large and geographically dispersed population, a multistage sampling technique is utilized (Isaac, 2023). Pakistan has a total of 145 public universities (List of universities in Pakistan, 2023). The first stage of sampling involves selecting seven public universities from Hazara region, considering the region's high literacy (67%) rate. A snowball sampling method is used in the second stage for choosing participants from the target population. This sampling technique is utilized to reach to those students who might not be easily contacted through traditional means (Woodley and Lockard, 2016). Earlier investigations have also used snowball sampling methods to examine the impact of gamification elements (Dewi, Mohaidin and Murshid, 2020; Tsou and Putra, 2023). Data was collected using Google Forms, and final analysis was carried out with total of 271 filled questionnaire. As per Comrey and Lee, (2013)) categorization of sample sizes based on statistical strength, sample size close to 300 is considered good.

Variables & Measures

All variables are measured using previous determined scales in order to ensure the reliability and accuracy. Five point Likert-type scale is used to measure each construct (see Appendix A).

Rewards: This variable is measured by a using a 4-item scale adapted from Tsou and Putra, (2023).

Points: This variable is measured by a using a 5-item scale adapted from Tsou and Putra (2023).

Enjoyment: This variable is measured by a using a 5-item scale adapted from Tsou and Putra (2023).

Customer Engagement: This variable is measured by a using a 4-item scale adapted from Tsou and Putra (2023).

Online Purchase Intention: This measure is assessed using a 5-item scale derived from Tümer et al., (2019).

Findings

Respondent's Profile

The respondent's profile shows a balanced gender distribution, a high level of education, a largely young adult population, and substantial past online buying experience (see table 1).

Table 1
Demographic Profile

Variable	N (271)	%
Gender		
Male	134	49.5
Female	137	50.5
Education Profile		
Undergraduate	182	67
Graduate	67	25
Post-Graduate	18	6.6
PHD/Doctoral	4	1.4
Age		
<18	6	2.2
18-25	224	82.6
26-30	26	9.6
31-40	12	4.4
41-50	3	1.2
Previous online shopping Experience		
Yes	263	97
No	18	3
Familiar with Gamified Platforms		
Yes	225	83
No	46	17

Descriptive Statistics

The mean values for all five variables are reasonably close together, ranging from 3.0 to 3.4, indicating that respondents had a moderate level of agreement on these features

of gamification and their effects (see table 2). The standard deviation values for all variables are close to 1.0, indicating that the responses vary moderately. All variables have negative skewness, which means their distributions have longer or fatter tails to the left. This suggests that most respondents evaluated these variables higher, clustering responses on the upper end of the scale (Field, 2013).

Table 2
Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
RW	3.3	1.1	-0.578	0.106
PO	3.3	1.0	-0.465	0.050
ENJ	3.4	1.0	-0.553	-0.102
CE	3.2	1.0	-0.530	-0.273
OPI	3.3	1.0	-0.694	0.610

Note(s): RW = Rewards, PO = Points, ENJ = Enjoyment, CE = Customer Engagement, OPI = online purchase intention

Correlation Analysis

Rewards (RW) and Points (PO) exhibit a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.496$, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that individuals who perceive rewards favorably also view points positively. A strong positive association ($r = 0.864$, $p < 0.01$) indicates that greater satisfaction with the gamified experience leads to a higher appreciation of points. Customer Engagement (CE) is significantly linked to both Enjoyment (ENJ) ($r = 0.737$, $p < 0.01$) and Points ($r = 0.752$, $p < 0.01$), emphasizing the role of enjoyment and perceived rewards in enhancing engagement. Furthermore, Online Purchase Intention (OPI) and Customer Engagement (CE) share a substantial positive relationship ($r = 0.676$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that higher engagement in gamified experiences increases the likelihood of making online purchases (see table 3).

Table 3
Correlation

	RW	PO	ENJ	CE	OPI
RW					
PO	.496**				
ENJ	.490**	.864**			
CE	.432**	.752**	.737**		
OPI	.469**	.659**	.659**	.676**	

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).**

Note(s): RW = Rewards, PO = Points, ENJ = Enjoyment, CE = Customer Engagement, OPI = online purchase intention,

Measurement Model

The study uses a factor analysis to identify the latent components that influence respondents' opinions of several gamification features. All variables Rewards, Points,

Enjoyment, Customer Engagement, and Online purchase intention showed higher factor loadings (see table 4).

Table 4
Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Variables	Indicators	Factor loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
Reward	RW1	.709	0.759	0.836	0.572
	RW2	.738			
	RW3	.712			
	RW4	.857			
Points	PO1	.797	0.863	0.869	0.709
	PO2	.861			
	PO3	.860			
	PO4	.849			
Enjoyment	ENJ1	.839	0.916	0.919	0.749
	ENJ2	.907			
	ENJ3	.880			
	ENJ4	.904			
	ENJ5	.792			
Customer Engagement	CE1	.840	0.910	0.913	0.788
	CE2	.909			
	CE3	.894			
	CE4	.906			
Online Purchase Intention	OPI1	.787	0.870	0.879	0.656
	OPI2	.803			
	OPI3	.835			
	OPI4	.830			
	OPI5	.794			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

Note(s): RW = Rewards, PO = Points, ENJ = Enjoyment, CE = Customer Engagement, OPI = online purchase intention

Construct Validity

Construct validity is evaluated through three essential indicators: Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, and average variance extracted (AVE).

Cronbach's alpha is an internal consistency reliability measure that explains how items on a concept or scale correlate with each other. Higher values of Cronbach's alpha represents reliable and consistent measurement instrument is All the variables in the current investigation show high internal consistency, ranging from 0.759 to 0.916, which is above the determined threshold value of 0.70.

Composite reliability measures the dependability of a latent construct by considering the factor loadings of the indicators. The threshold value for composite reliability is 0.7

(Hair Jr et al., 2021). All constructs in this study have composite reliability higher than the threshold value, ranging from 0.822 to 0.919, representing better reliability.

The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is measured through convergent validity, which refers to the closeness with which the items converge on to that construct. In simple words, convergent validity helps to make sure that items are measuring the constructs, which they are supposed to measure. Values of AVE greater than 0.50 are typically considered acceptable, indicating that the items represent the concept well (Hair Jr et al., 2021). All constructs in the present study have AVE values between 0.573 and 0.843, which shows that latent variables are demonstrating more than 50 percent of the variation.

Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity is a critical aspect of concept validation since it helps to confirm that measures used within a study are distinct from each other and that they do not target similar underlying constructs. In the current research, the absence of significant relationships between constructs shows that they are varied and measure distinct dimensions or concepts (see table 5).

Table 5
Discriminant Validity

	RW	ENJ	CE	OPI
RW				
PO	0.598			
ENJ	0.550	0.726		
CE	0.551	0.782	0.848	
OPI	0.623	0.705	0.694	0.762

Note(s): RW = Rewards, PO = Points, ENJ = Enjoyment, CE = Customer Engagement, OPI = Online Purchase intention

Hypotheses Testing

The outcome of the analysis provides meaningful insights into how different factors affecting Customer Engagement (CE) and Online Purchase Intention (OPI) are related. H1 predicted a relationship between Rewards (RW) and Customer Engagement (CE), but the direct influence of RW on CE is not significant (path coefficient = 0.025), thus failing to support H1. This suggests that Rewards by themselves could not be an effective driver of engagement, and perhaps other drivers may be more effective in driving customer engagement. Conversely, H2 predicted a link between Perceived Online Experience (PO) and CE and was supported with a significant path coefficient of 0.327. This implies that an improved online experience highly influences Customer Engagement, with a focus on the notion that a good user experience is key to growing consumer interaction with a site. H3 too investigates whether Enjoyment (ENJ) influences CE and finds a high path coefficient of 0.551. This confirms the notion that when customers are satisfied with their online shopping experience, they are more likely to interact with the site, which highlights the central position of enjoyment in driving engagement. For H4, the large direct effect of CE on OPI (path coefficient = 0.314) confirms the hypothesis that increased customer engagement results in higher

online purchase intentions. This draws attention to the significance of engagement as a purchase behavior driver, whereby customers who are engaged are more likely to purchase (see table 6).

Table 6
Hypotheses Testing Results

Hypotheses	Hypothesized Relationship	Total Direct Effects	Result
H1	RW → CE	0.025	H1 is not supported
H2	PO → CE	0.327***	H2 is supported
H3	ENJ → CE	0.551***	H3 is supported
H4	CE → OPI	0.314***	H4 is supported

Note(s): RW = Rewards, PO = Points, ENJ = Enjoyment, CE = Customer Engagement, OPI = online purchase intention

Mediation Testing

The results indicate that CE has a significant direct influence on OPI with a path coefficient of 0.336. The strong positive relationship indicates that greater consumer engagement is associated with more online purchase intent. The statistical significance of this relationship supports the hypothesis (H4) to the effect that customers' interaction has a direct influence on online buying behavior (see table 7).

Table 7
Results for Mediation

Hypothesized Relationship ENJ	Total Direct Effects CE --> OPI
Path Coefficient	0.336***
Results	H4 is supported

Note(s): CE = Customer Engagement, OPI = online purchase intention,

The results of the mediation analysis offer important insights into the potential mediating roles of Customer Engagement (CE) in the relationship between Rewards (RW) and Online Purchase Intention (OPI). For the Customer Engagement (CE) mediator, the direct effect of RW on CE is small (path coefficient = 0.025), and while the direct effect of CE on OPI is statistically significant (path coefficient = 0.314), the indirect effect through the CE pathway is not significant (path coefficient = 0.008). These findings suggest that even though CE has a strong direct influence on OPI, it does not significantly mediate the relationship between RW and OPI. Therefore, the hypothesis that CE mediates the effect of RW on OPI (H5a) is not supported, indicating no mediation in this case.

The results for the first pathway indicate a significant direct effect of PO on CE (path coefficient = 0.327), and a significant direct effect of CE on OPI (path coefficient =

0.314). The indirect effect through CE is also significant (path coefficient = 0.211), suggesting that Customer Engagement plays a role in linking Purchase Orientation (PO) to Online Purchase Intention (OPI). However, the direct effect of PO on OPI (path coefficient = 0.103) remains significant even after considering the mediator, indicating that PO has both a direct and indirect influence on OPI. These results support partial mediation, meaning that CE partially mediates the relationship between PO and OPI. Therefore, while Customer Engagement does mediate the relationship to some extent, PO still exerts a direct influence on OPI.

The mediation analysis investigated the roles of Customer Engagement (CE) as mediator in the relationship between Enjoyment (ENJ) and Online Purchase Intention (OPI). For the ENJ → CE → OPI pathway, the direct effect of ENJ on CE was significant (path coefficient = 0.551), and CE had a strong direct effect on OPI (path coefficient = 0.314). However, while the direct effect of ENJ on OPI was no longer significant (path coefficient = 0.085), the indirect effect through CE (ENJ → CE → OPI) was significant (path coefficient = 0.173). These findings suggest that Customer Engagement fully mediates the relationship between ENJ and OPI, meaning that ENJ influences OPI entirely through CE, and the direct effect of ENJ on OPI is eliminated when CE is included. Therefore, the hypothesis that CE fully mediates the effect of ENJ on OPI (H5c) is supported (see table 8).

Table 8
Results for Mediation

Hypothesized Relationship of RW	Direct Effect			Indirect Effects c'	Results
	a	b	c		
Path RW→CE→OPI	0.025	0.314***	0.189**	0.008	H5a is not supported No Mediation
Path PO→CE→OPI	0.327***	0.314***	0.211*	0.103**	H5b is supported Partial Mediation
Path ENJ→CE→OPI	0.551***	0.314***	0.085	0.173**	H5c is supported Full Mediation

Note(s): RW = Rewards, CE = Customer Engagement, OPI = online purchase intention, ENJ= enjoyment

Discussion

The current study explores how gamification elements impact customer engagement and purchase intention. One of the hypotheses tested the effect of the "Reward" element of gamification on customer engagement, but the results showed no significant impact, leading to the rejection of the hypothesis (H1). This suggests that rewards alone do not significantly boost customer engagement on online platforms. While rewards can attract users initially, the findings indicate they are not effective for fostering long-term engagement or strengthening customer relationships with the platform. According to Self-Determination Theory (Ryan and Vansteenkiste, 2023), the activities that are

inherently enjoyable (intrinsic motivation) play a significant role in fostering long-term engagement because rewards tend to deliver extrinsic motivation, they might not satisfy intrinsic needs like autonomy, competence, and relatedness that are necessary for long-term engagement. Therefore, rewarding without offering these psychological needs might not necessarily enhance engagement. The reward type also plays a role; generic rewards such as discounts or points might be less potent unless they are tailored to reflect personal tastes and behavior. Personalization of rewards through a user's history or interests can create more significant engagement. Timings and rewards distribution are also important determinants. Rewards given immediately offer immediate gratification, which has a greater tendency to increase engagement compared to its delayed counterpart (Cheng et al., 2012). In online buying, providing immediate rewards, like instant discounts on subsequent purchases, might be more attractive to consumers. Similarly, an affiliated hypothesis (5a) tested if Customer engagement mediates the relationship between rewards and online purchase intention. The findings indicated that rewards don't significantly enhance customer engagement, i.e., do not indirectly affect purchase intention through engagement. This implies that incentives exert a stronger influence on purchase intentions with tangible, extrinsic rewards such as coupons or cashback that stimulate purchases without depending on emotional or relational attachment. The idea that engagement-based approaches such as loyalty schemes or reward-basis gamification would boost purchase intention is also contradicted by the findings. Furthermore, the results did not support the mediation through interaction, which suggests that rewards are mostly used as transactional rewards, instead of developing the emotional connection between the customer and the platform. These conclusions are also supported by the earlier studies, such as Yi and Jeon,(2003) establishes that purchasing behavior is impacted by financial incentives without increasing overall engagement of the customers (Parris and Guzmán, 2023). The results supported the hypothesis H2, which highlights the significance of point systems via gamification in increasing customer participation. Point systems are widely used by businesses, which actually help them to increase engagement, interaction, and loyalty by setting up clear objectives. Customers are highly engaged by the instant feedback of points, which in returns enhance the feeling of progress, also in accordance with operant conditioning (Spielman et al., 2021). Moreover, points often act as social currency, which also promotes competition and social comparison, leading towards increased social influence, further driving user participation (Cialdini, 2001). In addition, points can be designed to form an escalating reward system. In terms of users earning points, they can achieve new levels, badges, or achievements as they continue their interest over time. Not only does this strategy keep users engaged, but it also increases their investment in the site. This aligns with the Goal-Setting Theory, suggesting that having clear and challenging goals enhances motivation and performance (Locke and Latham, 1990; Krath, Schürmann and Von Korflesch, 2021). Similarly, the confirmation of Hypothesis H5b Emphasizes the critical contribution of consumer involvement in translating the benefits of points into actual buying behaviors Although points themselves may encourage user involvement, it is the higher involvement that considerably affects purchase intentions. The result emphasizes the indirect manner by which gamification features like points affect online shopping behavior. The high mediation effect indicates that points contribute to fostering an active environment, ultimately leading to stronger purchase intentions. This aligns with the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), which posits that intentions, influenced by attitudes and perceived control, predict actual behavior. Engaged customers are more likely to spend time on the platform, explore products, and develop loyalty and trust,

increasing the likelihood of purchases. Emotional involvement is also a primary aspect since stronger-emoting customers are more likely to see greater value in products, and this will increase the likelihood of conversion. The mediation effect further implies that points, by themselves, might not drive purchases directly; instead, their strength is creating an interactive and engaging space. This emphasizes the importance of an integrated gamification strategy, wherein points are being integrated with incentives, badges, and social elements to boost the collective user experience.

The acceptance of H3 Hypothesis emphasizes enjoyment as a prominent driver of consumer participation on gamified online environments. Enjoyment, being a personal feeling of satisfaction and pleasure, motivates users to try to interact with gamified elements. The robust direct relationship between enjoyment and customer engagement indicates its importance in influencing user behavior. Since users appreciate their interactions, they are more likely to spend more time on the platform engaging in various activities and challenges. This is pursuant to the flow theory, where individuals derive profound enjoyment when they engage in tasks that suit their capabilities (Marougkas et al., 2023). Enjoyment is determined by elements including gaming mechanics, narrative, look and feel, interactivity, and sociality. The platforms offering these features assures enjoyable experiences for users leading towards their deeper engagement and affinity. Likewise, enjoyment reinforces emotional states, leading towards more satisfaction and positivity. Ultimately these feeling directs users to develop deep bonding with the platform. Earlier investigations have supported the notion that emotional engagement significantly influence to encourage user behavior particularly purchase intentions (Akram et al., 2021).

Besides, the approval of Hypothesis H5c emphasizes the role of customer engagement as a mediator between enjoyment and online purchase intention. The current findings demonstrates that, although enjoyment directly influences purchase intention, its impact is significantly strengthened by the mediator customer engagement. Enjoyment serves as the key motivator for customer engagement by generating positive feelings and happiness while experiencing gamified elements. Pleasing experiences like these assist users to get more engaged with the platform increasing their interaction. Consequently, customer engagement operates as a bridge, converting the advantage of enjoyment into increased purchase intention. Engaged users develop a more favorable attitude toward the platform, have stronger brand allegiance, and see greater value in its services. Attitudinal and behavioral changes make them more likely to purchase, driving the success of the platform. Customer engagement also increases the platform's credibility and trustworthiness, which play an overarching role in influencing purchase decisions. Customers who are deeply engaged developed the feeling of trust and confidence with the platform and then they are more likely to get product data, suggestions, feedback and willingness to purchase. The feeling of ownership and investment into the site encourages users to discover its functionality, exchange experiences, and communicate with other users, further developing their attachment and enhancing the probability of purchase. The confirmation of Hypothesis H4 emphasizes the role of customer engagement in determining consumers' online purchase intentions. Customer engagement refers to all various interactions, actions, and experiences users have on a platform, which collectively play an influential role in making users likely to purchase. Several theoretical models build a relationship between customer engagement and purchasing intent. The Theory of Reasoned Action (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1977) suggests that individuals' behavioral intentions are influenced by their attitudes toward the behavior and the perceived social pressure, or subjective norms, surrounding it. In the context of online shopping, increased

interaction with a platform can foster more positive attitudes toward purchasing and strengthen the social norms associated with online buying behavior. The Technology Acceptance Model (Marangunić and Granić, 2015) further proposes that perceived utility and ease of use are key predictors of consumers' intentions to adopt technology. Increased levels of engagement usually result from how users feel about the usefulness and simplicity of a platform, which further raises their purchase intention as the platform is perceived as convenient and useful. Customer engagement further promotes trust and loyalty, both of which are important drivers of purchase intentions (Habib, Hamadneh and Hassan, 2022). Engaged customers are inclined to perceive the platform as credible, trustworthy, and reliable, which further boosts their confidence in buying from it. Such trust promotes repeat purchases and customer loyalty over time. In addition, engagement is known to create a sense of emotional bonding with the platform (Pansari and Kumar, 2017). Emotional commitment is a powerful purchase intent driver because consumers are more likely to make a purchase if they are personally committed to a brand or platform. Active users can become positively emotionally associated with the platform, again strengthening their purchase intent to re-affirm these emotions.

Limitations & Future Implications

One of the limitations of the study is its sample size and demographics that were drawn from university students from a particular geographic location. The future studies should seek to have more extensive and diversified samples that span different ages, ethnicities, and locations to enhance the generalizability of findings. In addition, the cross-sectional nature of the study collecting data at a single point in time constrains the potential to make conclusions regarding causality or changes in behaviors over time to determine causality or monitor changes over time. Longitudinal studies would be required to monitor movement in customer participation and buying intent over time and allow for better understanding of causal relationships. Furthermore, this study is focused on specific gamification elements such as rewards, points, and enjoyment. However, gamification includes a wider array of elements, like leaderboards, badges, and challenges, which should be explored in future research to better understand gamification's overall effectiveness. Additionally, the study is conducted in the online retail context, and further research should explore gamification's effects in other domains to assess whether the findings hold across various industries. Finally, as digital platforms continue to advance, future studies should explore the effectiveness of gamification across diverse environments, including mobile applications, social media platforms, and e-commerce websites. Investigating cross-platform gamification can reveal unique user behaviors and platform-specific dynamics, enabling businesses to tailor and enhance their gamification strategies within different digital ecosystems.

References

- Ajzen, I. (1991) 'The theory of planned behavior', *Organizational behavior and human decision processes*, 50(2), pp. 179–211.
- Akram, U. et al. (2021) 'Online purchase intention in Chinese social commerce platforms: being emotional or rational?', *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 63, p. 102669.
- Alsawaier, R.S. (2018) 'The effect of gamification on motivation and engagement', *The International Journal of Information and Learning Technology*, 35(1), pp. 56–79.
- Amin, M.A. et al. (2023) 'The relationship between brand personality and purchasing intentions: An empirical study on customers of mobile phones in Saudi Arabia', *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 18(4).

- Ares, A.M. et al. (2018) 'Results of the use of Kahoot! gamification tool in a course of Chemistry', in 4th international conference on higher education advances (HEAD'18). Editorial Universitat Politècnica de València, pp. 1215–1222.
- Bozkurt, S., Gligor, D. and Gligor, N. (2022) 'Investigating the impact of psychological customer engagement on customer engagement behaviors: the moderating role of customer commitment', *Journal of Marketing Analytics*, 10(4), pp. 408–424.
- Bravo, R., Catalán, S. and Pina, J.M. (2023) 'The impact of gamified loyalty programmes on customer engagement behaviours. A hotel industry application', *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology*, 14(5), pp. 925–940.
- Chaffey, D. and Ellis-Chadwick, F. (2019) 'Digital marketing: strategy', *Implementation, and Practice* [Preprint].
- Chang, J.-W. and Wei, H.-Y. (2016) 'Exploring engaging gamification mechanics in massive online open courses', *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 19(2), pp. 177–203.
- Chans, G.M. and Portuguese Castro, M. (2021) 'Gamification as a strategy to increase motivation and engagement in higher education chemistry students', *Computers*, 10(10), p. 132.
- Chen, X. et al. (2021) 'Examining customer motivation and its impact on customer engagement behavior in social media: the mediating effect of brand experience', *SAGE open*, 11(4), p. 21582440211052256.
- Cheng, Y., Shein, P.P. and Chiou, W. (2012) 'Escaping the impulse to immediate gratification: The prospect concept promotes a future-oriented mindset, prompting an inclination towards delayed gratification', *British Journal of Psychology*, 103(1), pp. 129–141.
- Cialdini, R.B. (2001) 'The science of persuasion', *Scientific American*, 284(2), pp. 76–81.
- Clement, A.P. et al. (2021) 'Live-Streaming Consumer Experience; the Future of E-commerce and Digital Marketing in Africa: Evidence from China.', *International Journal of Information & Management Sciences*, 32(2).
- Comrey, A.L. and Lee, H.B. (2013) *A first course in factor analysis*. Psychology press.
- Dewi, C.K., Mohaidin, Z. and Murshid, M.A. (2020) 'Determinants of online purchase intention: a PLS-SEM approach: evidence from Indonesia', *Journal of asia business studies*, 14(3), pp. 281–306.
- Eroglu, S.A., Machleit, K.A. and Davis, L.M. (2003) 'Empirical testing of a model of online store atmospherics and shopper responses', *Psychology & marketing*, 20(2), pp. 139–150.
- Falco, G. (2020) 'Customer engagement through gamification marketing in China: a focus on the luxury market.'
- Fan, H., Han, B. and Gao, W. (2022) '(Im) Balanced customer-oriented behaviors and AI chatbots' Efficiency–Flexibility performance: The moderating role of customers' rational choices', *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 66, p. 102937.
- Field, A. (2013) 'Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS statistics'. sage London.
- Fishbein, M. and Ajzen, I. (1977) 'Belief, attitude, intention, and behavior: An introduction to theory and research'.
- Gao, Y. and Wu, Z. (2022) 'Does Gamification Increase Purchase Intention? A Systematic Review', in *International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction*. Springer, pp. 327–339.
- García-Jurado, A. et al. (2021) 'Does gamification engage users in online shopping?', *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 48, p. 101076.

- Gong, J. et al. (2023) 'Do privacy stress and brand trust still matter? Implications on continuous online purchasing intention in China', *Current Psychology*, 42(18), pp. 15515–15527.
- Gupta, A. and Gomathi, S. (2017) 'A review on gamification and its potential to motivate and engage employees and customers: Employee engagement through gamification', *International Journal of Sociotechnology and Knowledge Development (IJSKD)*, 9(1), pp. 42–52.
- Habib, S., Hamadneh, N.N. and Hassan, A. (2022) 'The relationship between digital marketing, customer engagement, and purchase intention via OTT platforms', *Journal of Mathematics*, 2022(1), p. 5327626.
- Hair Jr, J.F. et al. (2021) 'An introduction to structural equation modeling', *Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) using R: a workbook*, pp. 1–29.
- Harrigan, P., Evers, U., Miles, M., & Daly, T. (2017) 'Customer engagement with tourism social media brands', *Tourism management*, (59), pp. 597–609.
- Högberg, J. et al. (2019) 'Creating brand engagement through in-store gamified customer experiences', *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 50, pp. 122–130.
- Hwang, J. and Choi, L. (2020) 'Having fun while receiving rewards?: Exploration of gamification in loyalty programs for consumer loyalty', *Journal of business research*, 106, pp. 365–376.
- Jung, S., Lee, S.A. and Leitch, S. (2024) 'Examining the effect of gamification mobile app on conference engagement: an integration of SOR framework and UGT', *International Journal of Event and Festival Management [Preprint]*, (ahead-of-print).
- Keisidou, E., Sarigiannidis, L. and Maditinos, D. (2011) 'Consumer characteristics and their effect on accepting online shopping, in the context of different product types', *International Journal of Business Science & Applied Management (IJBSAM)*, 6(2), pp. 31–51.
- Koivisto, J. and Hamari, J. (2019) 'The rise of motivational information systems: A review of gamification research', *International journal of information management*, 45, pp. 191–210.
- Krath, J., Schürmann, L. and Von Korfflesch, H.F.O. (2021) 'Revealing the theoretical basis of gamification: A systematic review and analysis of theory in research on gamification, serious games and game-based learning', *Computers in human behavior*, 125, p. 106963.
- Kuswanto, H. et al. (2019) 'Analysis of students' online shopping behaviour using a partial least squares approach: Case study of Indonesian students', *Cogent Business & Management*, 6(1), p. 1699283.
- Laudon, K.C. and Traver, C.G. (2020) *E-commerce 2019: Business, technology, society*. Pearson.
- Leclercq, T., Poncin, I. and Hammedi, W. (2020) 'Opening the black box of gameful experience: Implications for gamification process design', *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 52, p. 101882.
- Lee, H.-Y. et al. (2023) 'Precision education via timely intervention in K-12 computer programming course to enhance programming skill and affective-domain learning objectives', *International Journal of STEM Education*, 10(1), p. 52.
- Locke, E.A. and Latham, G.P. (1990) *A theory of goal setting & task performance*. Prentice-Hall, Inc.
- Marangunić, N. and Granić, A. (2015) 'Technology acceptance model: a literature review from 1986 to 2013', *Universal access in the information society*, 14, pp.

81–95.

- Marougkas, A. et al. (2023) ‘Virtual reality in education: a review of learning theories, approaches and methodologies for the last decade’, *Electronics*, 12(13), p. 2832.
- Merrilees, B. (2016) ‘Interactive brand experience pathways to customer-brand engagement and value co-creation’, *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 25(5), pp. 402–408.
- Meyer-Waarden, L., Bruwer, J. and Galan, J.-P. (2023) ‘Loyalty programs, loyalty engagement and customer engagement with the company brand: Consumer-centric behavioral psychology insights from three industries’, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 71, p. 103212.
- Miri, D.H. and Macke, J. (2022) ‘Gamification, motivation, and engagement at work: a qualitative multiple case study’, *European business review*, 34(2), pp. 263–276.
- Mucollari, L. and Samokhin, V. (2017) ‘Gamification: The influence of gamification on the consumer purchase intention’.
- Mullins, J.K. and Sabherwal, R. (2020) ‘Gamification: A cognitive-emotional view’, *Journal of Business Research*, 106, pp. 304–314.
- Naqvi, M.H.A., Jiang, Y. and Naqvi, M. (2021) ‘Generating customer engagement in electronic-brand communities: a stimulus–organism–response perspective’, *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 33(7), pp. 1535–1555.
- Nicholson, S. (2015) ‘Peeking behind the locked door: A survey of escape room facilities’.
- Pansari, A. and Kumar, V. (2017) ‘Customer engagement: the construct, antecedents, and consequences’, *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 45, pp. 294–311.
- Parapanos, D. and Michopoulou, E. (2023) ‘Innovative mobile technology in hotels and the use of gamification’, *Tourism Planning & Development*, 20(2), pp. 162–187.
- Park, M. and Lennon, S.J. (2009) ‘Brand name and promotion in online shopping contexts’, *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management: An International Journal*, 13(2), pp. 149–160.
- Parris, D.L. and Guzmán, F. (2023) ‘Evolving brand boundaries and expectations: looking back on brand equity, brand loyalty, and brand image research to move forward’, *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 32(2), pp. 191–234.
- Prentice, C., Wang, X. and Loureiro, S.M.C. (2019) ‘The influence of brand experience and service quality on customer engagement’, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 50, pp. 50–59.
- Rakhmanita, A., Kusumawardhani, P. and Anggarini, D.T. (2023) ‘Gamification in teaching innovation: perception of teacher adaptation with the organism-response stimulus paradigm’, *Jurnal Education and Development*, 11(1), pp. 221–224.
- Rather, R.A., Hollebeek, L.D. and Islam, J.U. (2019) ‘Tourism-based customer engagement: The construct, antecedents, and consequences’, *The Service Industries Journal*, 39(7–8), pp. 519–540.
- Rehman, S.U. et al. (2019) ‘The moderating role of trust and commitment between consumer purchase intention and online shopping behavior in the context of Pakistan’, *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 9(1), pp. 1–25.
- Robert, D. and John, R. (1982) ‘Store atmosphere: an environmental psychology approach’, *Journal of retailing*, 58(1), pp. 34–57.
- da Rocha Seixas, L., Gomes, A.S. and de Melo Filho, I.J. (2016) ‘Effectiveness of gamification in the engagement of students’, *Computers in Human Behavior*, 58, pp. 48–63.
- Russell, J.A. and Mehrabian, A. (1974) ‘Distinguishing anger and anxiety in terms of

- emotional response factors.’, *Journal of consulting and clinical psychology*, 42(1), p. 79.
- Ryan, R.M. and Vansteenkiste, M. (2023) ‘Self-determination theory: Metatheory, methods, and meaning’, *The Oxford handbook of self-determination theory*, pp. 3–30.
- Sailer, M. et al. (2017) ‘How gamification motivates: An experimental study of the effects of specific game design elements on psychological need satisfaction’, *Computers in human behavior*, 69, pp. 371–380.
- So, K.K.F. et al. (2016) ‘Enhancing customer relationships with retail service brands: The role of customer engagement’, *Journal of Service Management*, 27(2), pp. 170–193.
- Spielman, R.M. et al. (2021) ‘What Is Learning?’, *Psychology-H5P Edition* [Preprint].
- Su, L. and Swanson, S.R. (2017) ‘The effect of destination social responsibility on tourist environmentally responsible behavior: Compared analysis of first-time and repeat tourists’, *Tourism Management*, 60, pp. 308–321.
- Sung, E.C. et al. (2022) ‘What drives technology-enhanced storytelling immersion? The role of digital humans’, *Computers in Human Behavior*, 132, p. 107246.
- Tobon, S., Ruiz-Alba, J.L. and García-Madariaga, J. (2020) ‘Gamification and online consumer decisions: Is the game over?’, *Decision Support Systems*, 128, p. 113167.
- Torres, P., Augusto, M. and Neves, C. (2022) ‘Value dimensions of gamification and their influence on brand loyalty and word-of-mouth: Relationships and combinations with satisfaction and brand love’, *Psychology & Marketing*, 39(1), pp. 59–75.
- Tsou, H.-T. and Putra, M.T. (2023) ‘How gamification elements benefit brand love: the moderating effect of immersion’, *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 41(7), pp. 1015–1036.
- Tümer, M. et al. (2019) ‘The impact of traditional and social media marketing on customers’ brand trust and purchase intentions in the Turkish airline market’, *Journal of Research in Emerging Markets*, 1(4), p. 55.
- Woodley, X.M. and Lockard, M. (2016) ‘Womanism and snowball sampling: Engaging marginalized populations in holistic research’, *The Qualitative Report*, 21(2), pp. 321–329.
- Xi, N. and Hamari, J. (2020) ‘Does gamification affect brand engagement and equity? A study in online brand communities’, *Journal of Business Research*, 109, pp. 449–460.
- Xu, G. et al. (2020) ‘Moving towards sustainable purchase behavior: examining the determinants of consumers’ intentions to adopt electric vehicles’, *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 27, pp. 22535–22546.
- Xu, X., Wu, J.-H. and Li, Q. (2020) ‘What drives consumer shopping behavior in live streaming commerce?’, *Journal of electronic commerce research*, 21(3), pp. 144–167.
- Yang, Y., Asaad, Y. and Dwivedi, Y. (2017) ‘Examining the impact of gamification on intention of engagement and brand attitude in the marketing context’, *Computers in Human Behavior*, 73, pp. 459–469.
- Yi, Y. and Jeon, H. (2003) ‘Effects of loyalty programs on value perception, program loyalty, and brand loyalty’, *Journal of the academy of marketing science*, 31(3), pp. 229–240.
- Yoong, L.C. and Lian, S.B. (2019) ‘Customer engagement in social media and purchase intentions in the hotel industry’, *International Journal of academic research in*

- business and social sciences, 9(1), pp. 54–68.
- Yusuf, A.S., Che Hussin, A.R. and Busalim, A.H. (2018) ‘Influence of e-WOM engagement on consumer purchase intention in social commerce’, *Journal of services Marketing*, 32(4), pp. 493–504.
- Zhu, L. et al. (2020) ‘How online reviews affect purchase intention: a new model based on the stimulus-organism-response (S-O-R) framework’, *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, 72(4), pp. 463–488.